

Biofilm growth monitoring using guided wave ultralong-range Surface Plasmon Resonance: A proof of concept

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Abstract

Unwelcomed biofilms are problematic in food industries, surgical devices, marine applications, and wastewater treatment plants; essentially everywhere where there is moisture. Very recently, label-free advanced sensors such as localised and extended surface plasmon resonance (SPR) have been explored as tools for monitoring biofilm formation. However, conventional noble metal SPR substrates suffer from low penetration depth (100 - 300 nm), preventing the reliable detection of large entities of single or multi-layered cell assemblies like biofilms which can grow up to a few micrometres or more. In this study we propose the use of a plasmonic insulator-metal-insulator (IMI) structure ($\text{SiO}_2\text{-Ag-SiO}_2$) with a higher penetration depth based on a diverging beam single wavelength format of Kretschmann configuration in a portable SPR device. The optimized IMI structure exhibits strong penetration dependence on wavelength and incidence angle. At the wavelength of 635 nm, a high penetration depth of more than 4 μm was obtained. Compared to a thin gold film substrate, for which the penetration

depth is only ~200 nm, the IMI substrate provides more reliable results. The average thickness of the biofilm after 24 h of growth were comparable for both the substrates (6 - 7 μm) estimated using confocal micrographs. Furthermore, when plasma-assisted degeneration of biofilms was studied in a semi-real time format there was almost no effect on the IMI substrate as compared to the gold substrate. Therefore, this methodology can be utilized to detect and characterize biofilms with better signal reliability in respect to concentration and size dependence.

Keywords: Biofilm, Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR), Portable SPR, GW-LRSPR

1. Introduction

A biofilm is a functional consortium of single or mixed-species populations of bacteria attached to a solid surface and embedded in an Extracellular Polymeric Matrix (EPS) produced by microorganisms (Bryers, 1984). This assembly consists of less than 10% of dry mass, with 90 % accounting for the matrix. An EPS consists of complex biopolymers, including proteins, lipids, glycopeptides, lipopolysaccharides, and extracellular nucleic acids which form the scaffold to hold the biofilm together and provides a protection from the environmental stress (Costerton, 1985). Biofilms are generally referred to as biofouling, which is defined as the undesirable formation of a layer of microorganisms on surfaces in contact with liquid media (Kumar and Anand, 1998). Biofilms are ubiquitous in our environment and their formation can lead to serious hygiene issues and economic losses. In the dairy and food industry, biofouling inhibits heat exchange, increases rates of corrosion, and causes health issues due to microbial contamination (Shi and Zhu, 2009; Srey et al., 2013; Carrascosa et al., 2021). They can clog membranes in water purification systems and even preclude UV treatment (Flemming and Geesey, 1991; Nguyen et al., 2012). From a medical perspective, biofilms on medical implants like catheters, artificial prosthetics, and contact lenses pose a serious threat to a patient's health, and increase the trauma and cost of treatment (Loiselle and Anderson, 2003; Mack et al., 2006; Hojo et al., 2009; Veerachamy et al., 2014; Jhajharia et al., 2015). It has been estimated that biofilms are associated with more than 65% of nosocomial infections (Potera, 1999). Indwelling infections because of biofilms, such as urinary tract infections, septic arthritis, chronic rhinosinusitis, oral and wound infections are usually recurrent and untreatable (Roberts et al., 2015; Fleming and Rumbaugh, 2018). The complex architecture of biofilms enables gene transfer among bacteria which leads to increased number of virulent strains (Gilbert et al., 2003). Bacteria embedded in biofilms (sessile form) show slower or complete resistance to the

changes in the chemical micro-environment compared to planktonic bacteria. This attribute causes slow penetration of antimicrobial agents and the immune system making pathogen elimination exceptionally difficult or sometimes impossible (Costerton et al., 1999; Percival et al., 2011). Since a variety of physiochemical mechanisms are involved in the growth and development of the myriad types of biofilms, their timely detection and characterization are of utmost importance to understand and devise suitable prevention and mitigation methods. For decades detection, quantification, and analysis of biofilms have been carried out by a variety of methods depending upon the application, target, and feasibility of sampling procedures. Plate counting, roll plate, acridine orange staining, streak plating of alginate swabs, tube method, congo-red agar, and microtiter plate assays are just a few of the indirect methods of biofilm detection (Bose et al., 2009; Kirmusaoğlu, 2019; Xu et al., 2020). These methods largely dependent upon cell sampling (Vertes et al., 2012). A slow-growing variant may not form colonies under routine laboratory conditions and may lead to false-negative results (Donlan and Costerton, 2002; Shen et al., 2010). Often, heterogeneous biofilms consist of fastidious or mixed species, which require stringent conditions to grow in detectable numbers using conventional methods (Fisher et al., 2017). Reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR), conventional, and multiplexed PCR are routine nucleic acid based-methods currently used to identify biofilm composition (Guilbaud et al., 2005; Cairns et al., 2011; França et al., 2012; Kirmusaoğlu, 2019). These DNA-based techniques though, fail in providing information about the viability of the cells and the distinction of the phenotype. However, this can be achieved with the expression of mRNA. Mass spectroscopy and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) are other sophisticated methods for phenotyping biofilms and assessing protein profiles (Kuboniwa et al., 2012; Seneviratne et al., 2012). Several imaging techniques are also used to observe the complexity, and dynamics of biofilms, such as light microscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and laser scanning confocal microscopy (LSCM) (Lawrence et al., 2003). Dyes, fluorescent protein gene expression and negative staining are therefore used to visualize the 3D architecture of biofilms (Boulos et al., 1999; Gustafsson, 2005; Gu et al., 2005; Peeters et al., 2008; Valour et al., 2013; Reichhardt et al., 2015). Other advanced approaches include impedance spectroscopy, quartz crystal microbalance (QCM), surface acoustic waves (SAW), surface plasmon resonance/imaging (SPR(i)), and surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) (Kim et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2012; Pires et al., 2013; Hohmann et al., 2015; Olsson et al., 2015; Ripa et al., 2020).

Although current methods are still very important and relevant for studying and understanding biofilms, there is an urgent need for a real-time evaluation to address different aspects of biofilm growth and elimination. SPR is one of the emerging label-free techniques in the field of biofilm detection and characterization. Owing to the high sensitivity of SPR-based sensors (10^{-7} RIU), the onset of bacterial cells attachment on a solid surface can be detected within a few hours. Since SPR-based sensors are extremely sensitive to the refractive index (R.I) change only near the immediate vicinity of the plasmonic surface, it is very useful to eliminate any signal from planktonic bacterial cells (Piliarik and Homola, 2009). This feature thus helps in discriminating between sessile and planktonic bacteria. Only a few attempts have been made to exploit the SPR phenomenon in biofilm analysis, usually with gold as metallic layer due to ease of surface modification and stability. Funari et al. (2018) showed the use of gold localized SPR for biofilm detection and the effect of different antibiotics on its growth (Funari et al., 2018). Similarly, Abadian et al. also conducted real-time monitoring of biofilm removal using SPRi (Abadian et al., 2014a; Abadian et al., 2014b; Abadian and Goluch, 2015). Filion-Côté et al. (2017) demonstrated real-time growth and removal of bacterial film using a 50 nm gold substrate (Filion-Côté et al., 2017).

The sensitivity and reliability of an SPR sensor heavily depends upon the penetration depth of the evanescent field, which decays exponentially in the direction normal to the substrate-analyte medium interface. Therefore, small penetration depth limits the reliable detection of cellular entities and multilayered biofilm architecture. For instance, conventional gold SPR substrates exhibit penetration depths up to 200 nm for wavelengths in the visible range, whereas biofilms can grow up to several to tens of micrometer thickness ($\sim 100 \mu\text{m}$) over weeks. It has been shown that such plasmonic sensors become saturated or fail in assessing the concentration and size dependence of the refractive index (Isaacs and Abdulhalim, 2015). To address this issue, we proposed an insulator-metal-insulator (IMI) structure that exhibits a long penetration depth of up to a few micrometers or more in the visible range. The bottom insulator layer (*e.g.* ~ 500 nm SiO_2) provides a plasmon wave propagating under the metal film and therefore can be used for reference purposes. The top insulator layer (which can also be ~ 500 nm SiO_2) acts as a waveguide so that guided wave SPR modes are excited. Upon specific design of the structure parameters, it was shown that when the resonance angle is close to the critical angle the penetration depth can become very large, starting from a few micrometers up to a few tens of micrometers, depending on the wavelength and angle. Under these conditions, the resonance width becomes very narrow, indicating long-range propagation (LRSPR)(Jing et al.,

2019). Vala et al. (2009) has calculated 5.5 higher response with LRSPR than conventional SPR for the detection of bacteria (Vala et al., 2009). Contrary to standard LRSPR in which a single insulator layer is buried under the metal layer, here the IMI structure provides guided wave long-range (GW-LRSPR) with a larger penetration depth. A small number of studies have demonstrated that standard LRSPR offers slightly higher penetration depth (Chabot et al., 2012; Shrivastav et al., 2021). Huang et al. (2012) used gold substrate supporting LRSPR to study the connection between *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and zwitterionic polymers (Huang et al., 2012). Isaacs and Abdulhalim (2015) have shown computationally and experimentally the need and utility of the IMI design for cell detection as it offers much greater penetration depth (Isaacs and Abdulhalim, 2015).

In this work, we demonstrated one such IMI format ($\text{SiO}_2\text{-Ag-SiO}_2$) for monitoring biofilm growth and removal. The evanescent field distribution and penetration depth of the GW-LRSPR sensor were calculated at a wavelength in the visible range using COMSOL Multiphysics (wave optics package). The addition of a dielectric layer (SiO_2) of R.I higher than the analyte medium below and above the metal provides two advantages: (i) the resonant dip corresponding to the surface plasmon (SP) wave from the buried dielectric layer is almost insensitive to analyte concentration changes and thus can be used as self-reference, ii) the dielectric on top of the metal is separated and sensitive to any change in the R.I near the surface. In addition to regular gold thin film, silver shows a more sensitive SPR response but has low chemical stability and biocompatibility. A bimetallic configuration where a thin layer of gold on a thicker silver layer can combine the advantage of both the metals (Bajaj et al., 2021). Hence, the performance of the IMI substrate was also compared with the plasmonic configuration (thin gold layer on top of a thicker silver layer).

A portable angular SPR device in Kretschmann configuration with a diverging beam scheme (PhotonicSys H5 SPR) was utilized to monitor the growth and removal of *E. coli* K12 ATCC 10798 biofilms. For more details on the H5 SPR instrument, see (Harpaz et al., 2019; Harpaz et al., 2020). To establish the advantage and utility of this device, we compared the performance of bimetallic and rationally designed IMI substrates. We also visualized the shift of SPR reflectance dip with a sessile bacterial cell concentration near the sensor surface. Additionally, 3D biofilms were observed with live/dead double stain using a laser scanning confocal microscope (LSCM). The percentage of live and dead bio-volume was calculated using IMARIS (Bitplane, Zurich, Switzerland). Furthermore, the thickness of biofilms grown over

24 h was calculated by performing 3D modelling using IMARIS software. We then performed a time-dependent plasma-assisted degradation of bacterial biofilm and semi-real-time removal monitoring on a portable SPR device. The plasma-assisted cleaning of biofilm further confirmed the re-useability and reliability of the obtained SPR signal from IMI. We anticipate that rationally designed GW-LRSPR substrates have the potential to complement existing conventional methods for real-time characterization and timely detection of biofilms and could also find the use in the screening of drugs and evaluating cleaning procedures.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

Luria-Bertani (LB) broth and LB agar, LIVE/DEAD *BacLight* Bacterial Viability Kit, SYTO-9, and propidium iodide (Invitrogen, Eugene, OR, USA, L7012) were procured from Thermofisher Scientific. Phosphate Buffer Saline (PBS), dextrose (+), and 0.22 μm syringe filters (Millipore) were purchased from Sigma (Israel). Isopropanol (IPA) and absolute ethanol were purchased from Bio-Lab Ltd (Israel). SF11 glass for SPR substrates was procured from Photonicsys. Also used were MilliQ water (Millipore, 18.2 M Ω cm @ 25 °C), *Escherichia coli* (*E.coli*) K12 strain, biological safety cabinet (level-2), orbital shaker incubator (37 °C), microtiter plate reader (Shimadzu UV-24500, Japan), Confocal microscope (Zeiss LSM 880). IMARIS (Bitplane, Zurich, Switzerland), and COMSOL Multiphysics and MATLAB for the analytical solution.

2.2. Bacterial culture

50% Glycerol stock of *E. coli* K12 strain was used to obtain independent bacterial colonies. Bacteria were grown on LB agar plates using the streaking method, and incubating at 37 °C for 48 h. Single bacterial colony was then used to cultivate a starter (primary culture) in 5 ml LB broth at 37 °C on an orbital shaker incubator (140 RPM) for 24 h. Further, a secondary culture was prepared by inoculating fresh LB broth using 1% of starter culture and incubated for ~2 h at the above-mentioned conditions to harvest *E. coli* cells in its mid-log phase. This was confirmed by measuring the optical density (OD) of 0.2 at 600 nm. Typically for *E. coli* cell

cultures, OD₆₀₀ of 1.0 counts for 8×10^8 CFU mL⁻¹. This concentration was diluted 100 times ($\sim 10^6$ CFU mL⁻¹) in a fresh medium (10% LB + 0.56 mM Glucose) to later inoculate the sensor surface for biofilm growth.

2.3. SPR substrate:

Details of the design and fabrication procedure of the bimetallic plasmonic substrate can be found elsewhere (Bajaj et al., 2021). The nomenclature “bimetallic” and “gold” will be used interchangeably thereafter for simplicity. For IMI substrates (a property of Photonicsys Ltd.), the different layers were custom designed and optimized according to desired penetration depth. Briefly, the thickness of the various layers from top to bottom was 420 nm (SiO₂), 40 nm (Ag), 480 nm (SiO₂) respectively. IMI substrates were procured from Photonicsys. The substrates were finally cleaned using IPA and MilliQ in bath sonication to remove contaminants/dust and dried with a gentle N₂ blow right before use.

2.4. Computational studies for designing the substrate:

To analytically calculate the reflectivity as well as the penetration depth of the field in the IMI and bimetallic configurations, we used an analytic solution based on Abeles matrices (Shalabney and Abdulhalim, 2010). The dielectric functions of the materials were interpolated based on data taken from the Sopra database (<http://sspectra.com/>). The code was implemented in MATLAB software. To qualitatively show the field penetration in the x-z plane, field distribution was plotted using COMSOL Multiphysics (wave optics package), which is based on the finite element method (FEM) - frequency domain. The incident beam was modeled as a plane wave propagating in the x-z plane. A Perfectly Matched Layer (PML) boundary condition was then imposed for the z-coordinate. Field monitors (called port boundary conditions) were placed at a fixed z position below and above the structure to detect beam transmission and reflection as a function of incident angle. Besides the fact that it was used as a reflectivity monitor, the port located at the interface between the prism and the bottom PML was used as an input port for excitation. Adaptive mesh size (with tetrahedral elements) was used over the different physical domains to achieve accurate and reliable calculations, where a swept mesh was used for the PML domains.

2.5. Equipment:

The SPR biosensor platform (H5 SPR, PhotonicSys) was used for R.I signal acquisition and biofilm growth monitoring. The plasmonic substrates were installed inside the factory-calibrated SPR biosensor platform. However, the platform required further calibration to accommodate any temperature and humidity changes, which can be achieved by monitoring the pixel value of solutions with a well-known R.I. In this study, the calibration was conducted

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of monitoring biofilm growth using angular SPR

by monitoring the pixel value of MilliQ water and absolute ethanol. Subsequently, the known R.I value of water (1.3325) and absolute ethanol (1.3657) was used to calibrate the pixel value accordingly. The SPR biosensor platform detected the location of the dark line (minimum of reflectance) in pixels through a camera connection. Then, the shift in the R.I signal was monitored with a line detection algorithm. The line detection algorithm first identified the change in pixels, which was further translated into a shift in R.I. A schematic diagram depicting the typical setup of biofilm growth examination is shown in Fig. 1.

2.6. Inoculation of *E. coli* for biofilm growth

Flow channels were assembled, and pressure sealed on the plasmonic sensing surface in the SPR device as shown in Fig. 1. To maintain sterile conditions, the channels were flushed with 70% absolute ethanol for 30 min at a flow rate of $20 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ followed by rinsing the channels with sterile water prior to inoculation. Further, the sensor surface was equilibrated with the

biofilm growth medium (10 % LB + 0.56 mM Glucose) at a flow rate of 20 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ for 30 min to obtain a stable baseline. 200 μL of 100 times diluted ($\sim 10^6$ cells mL^{-1}) inoculum of *E. coli* was then injected into the analyte channel. The channels were carefully covered with parafilm to maintain sterile conditions. Static biofilm growth was then monitored for ~ 24 h at room temperature.

Additionally, for comparison, biofilms were grown at room temperature under sterile conditions. For imaging static biofilm growth, 3 x 3 mm sterile pieces of plasmonic substrates were incubated in 96-well optical plates (Thermo Scientific, Rochester, NY, USA). After staining, the substrates were placed upside down with the help of sterile tweezers to observe under the confocal microscope.

2.7. Confocal microscopy

Morphology and quality of *E. coli* biofilm on the plasmonic surfaces were observed by using the LIVE/DEAD *BacLight* double staining kit. Briefly, the medium was carefully removed from the channels. SYTO-9 and propidium iodide from the staining kit were mixed in equal volumes of 1.5 μL each in 1 mL of sterile water. 200 μL of the dye mixture was injected into both the channels gently and incubated for 15 min at room temperature. Further, the dye mixture was removed, and channels were washed with PBS three times. The flow channels were then removed carefully and plasmonic substrates were reversed on a sterile coverslip to face the objective lens of an inverted confocal microscope. The images were taken with Plan-Apochromat 40 x objective lens/1.3 oil DIC M27. The green channel for live cell detection was imaged using a 488-nm argon laser with emission filter bandpass 493-565. The red channel for dead cell detection was imaged using a 561 nm diode-pumped solid-state laser with emission filter bandpass 571 - 718. The scanning resolution was kept at 512 x 512 pixels. All the images were taken in Z-stack mode (0.5 μm interval) to realize the volume and thickness of the biofilm. 3D images were obtained and further analysed using IMARIS software (Bitplane, Zurich, Switzerland)

2.8. Plasma cleaning of the biofilms

To establish the scope of the portable SPR device and the quality of the proposed substrate design, the biofilms were cleaned using Ar/O₂ and Ar/N₂ plasma for the gold and IMI substrates

respectively. Briefly, for this study *Staphylococcus epidermidis* ATCC 39584 was used as a model bacterium. Bacterial cultures were prepared from a single colony inoculated into 5 mL of Tryptic Soy Broth (TSB) medium and incubated at 37 °C in a shaking incubator, Stuart SI500 (Bibby Scientific, Staffordshire, UK) at 200 rpm. The overnight cultures were adjusted with fresh TSB medium to obtain an optical density (OD_{600}) of 0.1. Substrates were inserted into 6-well cell culture plates in 10 ml of TSB medium. A bacterial concentration of 1×10^5 CFU mL⁻¹ was added to each well and incubated at 37 °C with a stirring rate of 60 rpm. After 24 h incubation, samples were rinsed several times with 0.9 % saline solution to remove planktonic bacteria. Plasma specifications were chosen for bimetallic and IMI substrates as Ar/O₂ and Ar/N₂ (80:20 sccm), respectively, with RF 100 W; pressure- 13 Pa; and sample position 25 cm away from the centre of the coil.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1.1 Computational studies

To calculate the penetration depth of the field in the IMI configuration, we used an analytic solution based on the Abeles matrices (Shalabney and Abdulhalim, 2010). First, the angular reflection of the different configurations is shown in Fig. 2a and 2b for TM polarization at 635 nm (black curve) and 532 nm (red curve). The IMI configuration is SiO₂-Ag-SiO₂ with thicknesses 420–40–480 nm. The bimetallic configuration is Ti-Ag-Au with thicknesses 2–37–10 nm. The dielectric functions of the materials were interpolated based on the data taken from the Sopra database (<http://sspectra.com/>). The analyte R.I was set to 1.335 in all simulations.

Figure 2. Angular reflectivity of IMI (a) and bimetallic (b) configurations at 635 nm (black curve) and 532 nm (red curve). Magnetic field enhancement was compared at resonance angles calculated in a) and b) respectively for bimetallic (c) and IMI (d) at different incident wavelengths. e) Magnetic field distribution as a function of angle of incidence for the IMI substrate f) Magnetic field distribution comparison of bimetallic configuration and the IMI configuration at their associated resonant angles at 635 nm incident wavelength and TM polarization calculated using COMSOL Multiphysics to present and compare the field penetration in both cases. The analyte index was set to 1.335 R.I for all simulations and the incidence angle is inside the SF11 glass prism.

The penetration depth (δ) is defined as the distance at which the field amplitude arrives at $1/e$ from its value at the interface. Therefore, an assessment of the performance of the IMI configuration at 635 nm and 532 nm was shown (Fig. 2c) to illustrate the influence of the incident wavelength, in which the resonant angle was calculated for each case (Fig. 2a). At 532 nm, a significant reduction in δ can be seen (389 nm) in comparison to 635 nm (4.139 μm). Further, Fig. 2e shows (at different angles for IMI), δ at the resonant angle (48.686°) equals 4.139 μm while at 48.676° and 48.696° , δ is 14.19 μm and 2.992 μm , respectively. Upon shifting the incident angle by 0.01° from resonance, δ was increased from 4.139 μm to 14.19 μm , which is considered a very significant improvement. Hence, we conclude that within the spatial frequencies (angles) distribution inside the resonance region, there is a distribution of penetration depths. When detecting the minimum position of the SPR line, all these signatures from the different spatial frequencies contribute to the final result. For example, the signal at 48.696° , gives information from the deeper region (14 - 15 μm) while at 48.676° , the information represents what is inside the region up to 4 - 5 μm . The purpose of this comparison was to highlight the sensitivity of δ to the incident angle. In addition, from a practical point of view, it is important to highlight the fact that a much larger δ can be achieved by tuning the incident angle between the TIR angle in which δ becomes infinite (propagating wave) and the resonant angle. It is important to note that larger δ is achieved closer to the TIR angle. More importantly, this shows that using the IMI configuration, one can design δ to match the target size to be sensed in the specific application. This property will be investigated further as it can give a new type of depth-resolved spectroscopy to monitor different depths simultaneously. Magnetic field distribution for the anti-symmetric mode at the resonant angle 48.686° as a function of the distance from the prism interface is shown in Fig. 2e (blue curve).

In comparison, for the bimetallic configuration shown in Fig. 2b a 635 nm, the reflection dip was obtained at 54.406° while at 532 nm, the dip was red shifted to 57.691° . The values of δ achieved at 635 nm and 532 nm were 182 nm and 118 nm, respectively, which are typical values for the prism-assisted pure plasmonic structure case (Fig. 2d).

Finally, a direct comparison between δ of the IMI and bimetallic configurations at the resonance condition and at 635 nm is shown in Fig. S1. As mentioned above, δ of $4.139\ \mu\text{m}$ and 182 nm were achieved for the IMI and bimetallic configurations, respectively, exhibiting significant improvement of δ by a factor of around 22 at resonance, which can be improved further by tuning the incident angle for IMI as discussed above. Moreover, to qualitatively show the field penetration in the x-z plane, we plotted field distribution using COMSOL Multiphysics. 635 nm incident wavelength, 1.335 R.I for the analyte material, and TM polarized light were used in the simulation. As presented in Fig. 2f, the penetration depth at resonance of the IMI configuration is around $4.5\ \mu\text{m}$, while for the bimetallic configuration it is around 200 nm. Both values are comparable to the analytical calculation of the penetration depth in Fig. 2c and 2d.

3.2. Monitoring biofilm growth using GW-LRSPR

E. coli K12 static biofilms were grown on gold and IMI substrates. The growth was continuously monitored using a miniaturized SPR device for 24 h at room temperature. The growth curve is shown in Fig. 3a and 3c, where the black curve corresponds to the reference medium and the red curve refers to biofilm growth with time. The curves were smoothed using Origin Pro 8. Growth time versus change in R.I was also plotted by subtracting the reference signal from the growth medium (Fig. 3 b, d). Fig. 3e and 3f are camera images of reflected light where SPR dip can be seen as the darker region for reference and analyte channels.

The initial increase in R.I. corresponds to bulk R.I caused by suspended bacteria in the growth medium. The signal then started to vary as bacterial cells began to adhere to the sensor surface. It is understood that the adhesion time varies with different types of solid surfaces. However, the overall SPR signal from the gold surface is not monotonic with biofilm growth as incubation time increases. One can argue that planktonic bacterial cells can keep attaching and detaching from adherent cells, which could explain the non-monotonic nature of the SPR signal. However, such changes should be seen in the first few hours of growth. Once the biofilm matures, the overall change in the cell density near the surface is not expected to vary

significantly. Therefore, keeping this in consideration, the IMI substrate showed a local variation in signal, followed by an overall increment in signal with an increase in cell density over the growth period. Since bacteria are thicker than the penetration depth offered by the gold substrate (~200 nm), Filion- Côté et al (2017) required additional methods to calculate the R.I at the resonant angle location. It was clear from their studies that the observed R.I changes due to bacterial growth was non-monotonic and suffered from interference from bulk R.I changes due to the formation of EPS (Filion-Côté et al., 2017).

We calculated the average thickness of the biofilm after 24 h of growth between 6 - 7 μm for both the substrates using 3D image processing of confocal micrographs (Section 3.3). It is evident from the SPR signal that attachment of sessile bacteria can be detected within less than 4 h for the IMI substrate, whereas for the gold substrate, the attachment of bacterial cells on the surface could not be detected reliably, because of the non-linear relationship between signal and cell density near the sensor surface. In addition, saturation for the IMI substrate was reached after 0.006 of change in R.I (Fig. 3d), whereas the gold substrate saturated much earlier than 0.003 of change in R.I (Fig. 3b) for similar thicknesses of biofilm on both substrates. These observations, in conjunction with computational calculations of field distribution, suggest that the IMI substrate holds an advantage over conventional gold substrates in monitoring biofilm growth *in-situ*. It is also quicker than other techniques like the tube method, which takes up to a day to detect biofilms (Kirmusaoglu, 2019) .

Bimetallic substrate

IMI substrate

Bimetallic substrate

IMI substrate

Figure. 3 Real-time monitoring of *E. coli* K12 biofilm growth on bimetallic and IMI plasmonic surfaces for 24 h. a) and c) monitoring R.I change. b) and d) Change in R.I with respect to a reference channel. SPR images of the sensing area on the bimetallic (e) plasmonic surface and (f) IMI. Arrow indicates the injection of inoculum in the analyte channel.

Since biofilm formation is a dynamic process, where bacterial cells attach, detach and migrate constantly (William Costerton, 1985), the SPR signals in Fig. 3a and 3c naturally highlight significant disturbances. Nonetheless, the overall R.I change is greater than the noise.

3.3. Confocal micrograph

Confocal images were obtained using LIVE/DEAD *BacLight* double staining kit to observe the morphology and quality of the biofilm. Equal volumes of the dye mixture were injected into the reference and analyte channels to stain the biofilm, followed by a gentle wash with PBS. 3D images obtained in z-stacking mode with an interval of 0.5 μm were used to calculate the percentage of live and dead biomass volume and to measure the average thickness. Images were taken at eight different locations on both SPR substrates, where each location had an area of 354 x 354 μm^2 . Biofilm volumes were calculated using IMARIS.

The morphology of *E. coli* biofilm grown on glass substrate was also compared at room temperature. The results can be found in supplementary files (Fig. S2 - S4). We found no significant distinction in the morphologies of the *E. coli* K12 biofilm for gold and IMI substrates. However, glass obviously supports more uniform and denser biofilm attachment. The average biofilm thickness after 24 h growth in the SPR device was found to be between 6 - 7 μm for both gold and IMI substrates. This implies that there was no significant influence of the type of substrate on biomass accumulation or thickness. However, one can see the difference in the percentage of live and dead bacterial cells for different substrates. It also, implies that bacteria exhibited more adhesion affinity for SiO_2 than gold. This also correlates with SPR signal response, where an increase in R.I due to increase in bacterial density near the surface started to be observed around 4 h after inoculation for the IMI substrate (Fig. 3 c, d). Additionally, the R.I increase was also significantly larger (~double) for IMI over the bimetallic substrate. Bacterial adhesion to the substratum is a complex phenomenon where various properties of the substrate, such as wettability, surface roughness, topography, *etc.*, play a co-dependent role (Zheng et al., 2021). Surface charge is one of the important factors affecting the motility and architecture of the bacterial cells biofilm formation (Guo et al., 2013).

Initial biofilm attachment is governed by the physio-chemical properties of the substratum. Gram-negative bacteria like *E. coli* experience a repulsive force from the negatively charged

Bimetallic substrate

IMI substrate

Figure 4. IMARIS processed 3D images of live (a) and dead (b) volume of *E. coli* K12 biofilm after 24 h of growth on a bimetallic substrate, c) combined channel, d) Average live and dead volumes calculated. IMARIS processed 3D images of live (e) and dead (f) volume of *E. coli* K12 biofilm after 24 h of growth on the IMI substrate. g) combined channel. h) Average live and dead volumes calculated. Scale: 50 μm

substrate in the beginning (Terada et al., 2012; Rzhapishevska et al., 2013). When plasmons are being excited in a thin gold film substrate, an oscillation of negative charge occurs, which might be a reason why bacteria are repelled from the surface in the beginning. On the other hand, with the IMI substrate, the evanescent wave near the SiO_2 top surface is a leaky guided wave and has no charges associated with it. We propose this mechanism as a possible reason for the difference between the two surfaces. SiO_2 coatings have been used in biocompatible medical implants like stents for the prevention of corrosion (Pietka et al, 2014) . For this reason, our study of bacteria growth on an IMI substrate (with SiO_2) is relevant to investigating biofilms in medical applications.

3.4. Monitoring of biofilm cleaning using Plasma

It is important to characterize and monitor biofilms removals from the SPR substrate for field applications. To demonstrate one such method, we used two different types of plasma for gold and IMI substrates. Details of the plasma specifications were mentioned in section 2. *S.*

Fig 5. Average pixel number measurement at different times of plasma exposure for biofilm removal on a) Bimetallic substrate and b) IMI substrates.

epidermidis ATCC 39584 biofilms were grown on gold and IMI substrates. For every 5 min of plasma exposure, SPR measurements were taken. Due to limitations of incorporating plasma cleaning in real-time, the SPR device could not be calibrated for the R.I, therefore the pixel numbers were taken into account for the signal. The effect of the plasma on the bare substrate was also considered. It was found that plasma exposure had some effect on the gold substrate after 20 s, but the IMI substrate was surprisingly stable for a longer time (Fig. 5 a, b).

Figure 6. SPR image obtained at a different times of plasma exposure for biofilm removal on a) bimetallic and b) IMI substrates.

SPR with imaging has the advantage of clearly visualizing the change in R.I near the sensor surface. The horizontal red lines in the SPR image panel in Fig. 6 depicts a gradual shift due to biofilm degradation upon plasma treatment.

4. Conclusions

Biofilms are ubiquitous and a constant threat to human health, the economy, and the environment. A fast and inexpensive detection method is needed. In this work, a promising SPR-based approach has been demonstrated and discussed as a method to address this issue. Several SPR-based sensors have already been used for biofilm detection. However, nearly all of them suffer from low evanescent wave penetration depth offered by conventional gold substrates, which prevents reliable detection and incurs signal ambiguity. Here, a proof-of-concept SPR-based sensor for the detection of larger entities like bacterial cells was presented, highlighting the importance of high penetration depth. A rational SPR substrate design over conventional gold substrates was elaborated and examined using computational tools. Based on previous studies from our group; (Isaacs and Abdulhalim, 2015) it was found that the IMI SPR substrates offer a better alternative. The penetration depths for IMI and gold were calculated to be more than 4.5 μm and less than 300 nm, respectively. In this work, the concept was tested using *E. coli* biofilms. *E. coli* biofilms were grown on IMI and gold SPR substrates and monitored in real-time. In the case of the IMI substrate, signal increase could be seen from 4 h of inoculation which is rapid compared to conventional biofilm detection methods. The *E. coli* biofilms were stained with live/dead dye to visualize the morphology using confocal microscopy. Percentages of live and dead volumes were also calculated and averaged over different areas of inspection on the SPR substrates. An average biofilm thickness between 6 - 7 μm was attained from 3D image processing of confocal micrographs. In addition, time-dependent biofilm disintegration on plasma exposure was also monitored using IMI and gold substrates. A linear (monotonic) SPR response was obtained in the case of the IMI substrate before reaching saturation. Plasma cleaning of the IMI substrate was shown to recover the surface of SiO_2 completely, while the gold surface experienced degradation. A judicious design and further improvement in the optimization of thickness of different layers in the IMI architecture is a promising approach for SPR-based sensors in monitoring the growth conditions, environment, antibiotic resistance, and effect of different drugs on biofilms. Furthermore, the strong angular and wavelength dependence of penetration depth using the IMI substrate may be used as depth-resolved spectroscopy to obtain information on different layers independently.

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Author's contribution: AB planned and performed the experiments, analysed the results, wrote the manuscript; MA corroborated computation studies and wrote the manuscript. SI took part in conceptualization and initiation of computational studies. M J.A- Development and assistance in maintaining the functional operation of the miniaturized SPR device (PhotonicSys H5). KY helped in microbial culture and confocal microscopic studies. AK helped in designing biofilm growth experiment, in providing microbiological facility and wrote manuscript. MM helped in microbial culture and assisting in plasma cleaning experiments. UC was responsible for project initiation and providing plasma facility. IA conceptualized the project, provided funding, wrote, and review the manuscript, and supervised the whole project.

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